

Full title: **Clean clinker production via calcium looping process**

Acronym: **CLEANKER**

Type of action: **H2020-LCE-2016-2017/LCE-29-2017**

Grant Agreement number: **764816**

Project starting date – Duration: **1st October 2017 – 48 months**

Design and full specifications of the pilot facility for mineralization tests in Vernasca

WP7 – Deliverable D7.5

Deliverable number	D7.5
Deliverable title	Design and full specifications of the pilot facility for mineralization tests in Vernasca
Work package	WP7: Transport, utilization and storage study
Due delivery date	30 September 2019 (M24)
Actual delivery date	8 October 2019
Deliverable Leader	BUZZI
Dissemination level (PU, CO)	PU

PU=Public

CO=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Key word(s)

CO₂ mineralization reactor – Reactor design – Instrumentation

Short description

The main objective of this task is the design and specification of a large device for the mineralization of CO₂ from the Vernasca demonstration plant. The reactor should be designed in order to replicate on a large scale the CO₂ mineralization test already obtained at lab scale.

History of changes

Version	DATE	Changes	Author
V1	2019-10-08	First release	Fulvio Canonico (BUZZI)

Abstract

Based on the lab-scale experiments and the resulting recommendations presented in deliverable D7.4, the CO₂ mineralization reactor to be integrated and tested in Vernasca demonstration plant has been designed. A commercially available concrete mixer will be properly modified and equipped with instrumentation to serve as semi-batch mineralization reactor.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Mineralization of gaseous CO₂ into thermodynamically stable carbonates is a promising method for the permanent storage of CO₂.

Deliverable D7.4 (Uibu et al., 2018) tested the carbonation of different types of wastes: burnt oil shale, concrete demolition wastes, cement by-pass dust and blast furnace slag. The wet direct carbonation method was adopted, with 0.2 – 0.3 w/w liquid to solid ratio and 20 – 70% CO₂-rich gas flow. The tests showed that the free lime content could be exhausted with 30 min in the conditions of low liquid to solid ratio and gas flow of 70% CO₂ in air.

The CO₂ uptake was mainly attributed to the free lime content, which is relatively high (10 – 37%) in burnt oil shale and cement by-pass dust samples, but non-existent in concrete demolition wastes and blast furnace slag. The role of Ca-Mg-silicates is considerably smaller. In case of fine burnt oil shale samples, 5 – 12% of CO₂ bound could be attributed to Ca-silicates, whilst the carbonation treatment did not have any effect on noticeably coarser blast furnace slag that consists mainly of Ca-silicates: therefore, in order to bind CO₂ into Ca-silicates, the slag needs additional pre-treatment by milling and/or a different carbonation route has to be considered.

The increase in flow rates was shown to accelerate the CO₂ mineralization process due to improved contact of phases. On the other hand, the variation of mixing speed (from 300 rpm to 3000 rpm) and CO₂ concentration in the gas stream (from 20% to 70%) did not significantly affect the process performance.

The main objective of this deliverable is the design of a large (> 100 L) mineralization reactor integrated with the CLEANKER pilot plant in Vernasca, based on the outcome of D7.4. The reactor will allow to mineralize part of the CO₂ captured during CLEANKER experimental campaigns.

2. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE REACTOR DESIGN

The main recommendations highlighted in deliverable D7.4 (Uibu et al., 2018) for the CO₂ mineralization reactor design are:

- Reactor type and volume. Commercially available Eirich intensive mixer of 100 – 500 L would guarantee an excellent contact of phases and high CO₂ binding rates. Furthermore, the tests performed in a 46 L concrete mixer showed that this type of standard apparatus is also suitable as CO₂ mineralization reactor. The latter option would also have the possibility to be relatively easily scaled-up by using commercial concrete trucks (5000 - 6000 L);
- CO₂ gas analyzer. This instrumentation is needed to continuously measure the CO₂ content of the gas leaving the reactor, the main indicator of carbonation efficiency. A Duotec Infrared CO₂ analyzer (0 – 10%) has been adopted for the tests carried out in D7.4;
- CO₂ inlet speed: 4.5 ± 2 m/s;
- Distance of the inlet openings from the bottom: 10 – 15 mm;
- Temperature sensors;
- Moisture sensors;
- Measures for avoiding the formation of precipitations and dead zones on the walls of the apparatus.

3. DESIGN OF THE CO₂ MINERALIZATION REACTOR

The CO₂ mineralization reactor will be of the semi-batch type. The batch charge will consist of the solid material to be carbonated, as well as the amount of water which may be added depending on the kind of solid. On the other hand, the CO₂-rich gas produced by CLEANKER oxyfuel calciner will be continuously fed to the reactor, while the CO₂-lean gas will be continuously extracted by means of a suction pump. A conceptual scheme of the mineralization reactor which will be installed in Vernasca is depicted in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1. Conceptual scheme of the CO₂ mineralization reactor.

Possible alternative Fig 3.1 (in case, sensors and other instrumentation should be added in the correct position)

In order to follow the aforementioned recommendations, it was decided to modify a commercially available concrete mixer for the realization of the mineralization reactor.

A Controls 55-C0199/20 pan type mixer has been selected for this purpose. Pan type models are a common choice for the preparation of concrete specimens and samples for laboratory use, since they assure the best uniformity and efficient mixing. The main characteristics of the mixer are reported in Table 3.1, while a picture is shown in Figure 3.2 (Controls Group, 2019).

Table 3.1. Main parameters of Controls 55-C0199/20 mixer.

Parameter	Value
Pan capacity (L)	300
Mixing capacity (L)	160-200
Power (kW)	5.5 (380-400 V, 50 Hz, 3 ph)
Overall dimensions (l x d x h) (mm)	1250 x 1200 x 1300
Weight (kg)	340

Figure 3.2. Controls 55-C0199/20 mixer.

The concrete mixer will undergo the following modifications in order to be connected to the CLEANKER pilot plant:

- replacement of the existing cover with a metal sheet equipped with a rubber gasket. The new cover will feature 2 openings to allow the connection of 2 pipes: (i) one for the CO₂-rich inlet stream and (ii) one for the CO₂-lean outlet stream;
- connection to the existing CLEANKER pilot by means of a 1” pipe (length ~ 6 m);
- installation of a perforated manifold for a good distribution of the inlet gas in the mineralization reactor;
- installation of a flowmeter on the CO₂ inlet pipe;

- installation of a suction pump on the gas outlet pipe;
- installation of a CO₂ sensor on the gas outlet pipe. On the other side, CO₂ concentration at the reactor inlet will be measured by the gas analyzer installed at the pilot plant;
- installation of temperature and moisture sensors.

3.1 Connection to the CLEANKER pilot

A fraction of the CO₂-rich gas produced by the calciner will be brought to the 4th floor of the preheater tower, where the mineralization reactor will be installed, through a DN 100 pipe, equipped with a 2” ball valve at the outlet. The ball valve, which will serve as connection point between the CLEANKER pilot and the mineralization system, will then be connected to the reactor inlet port by means of the previously mentioned 1” pipe.

The connection between the CLEANKER pilot and the ball valve is shown in Figure 3.3, Figure 3.4 and Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.3. CLEANKER pilot – mineralization reactor connection.

Figure 3.4. CLEANKER pilot – mineralization reactor connection.

Figure 3.5. CLEANKER pilot – mineralization reactor connection.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 764816. This work is supported by the China Government (National Natural Science Foundation of China) under contract No.91434124 and No.51376105.

4. PROCEDURE FOR START-UP OF THE CO₂ MINERALIZATION REACTOR

Adding solid material (20-60 kg oil shale ash) into the reactor (100L) and start mixing;

Adding water (0.2L/kg) and continuous mixing until the solid sample is evenly hydrated (2-5 minutes). The agglomeration and formation of paste must be avoided. The gas inlet tube should work on (A – air or B - CO₂ rich gas) during hydration in order to avoid clogging of the tube;

Continuous monitoring of reactor temperature;

Sampling before CO₂ mineralization treatment (a 10 grams): analysis of moisture content, total carbon and free lime content of the solid sample;

Starting CO₂ mineralization treatment: open valve for gas inlet (CO₂ rich gas 200-600L/kg ash) and suction for gas outlet;

Continuous monitoring of gas flow, CO₂ content, moisture content and temperature of gas inlet and outlet;

Continuous monitoring of reactor temperature;

Sampling (a 10 grams every 10 minutes): analysis of moisture content, total carbon and free lime content of solid samples

CO₂ mineralization treatment stops when CO₂ content in outlet equals CO₂ content in inlet gas

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